
Designing Southern Ocean E(B)V workflows, from data collection to data products

WORKSHOP REPORT

Designing Southern Ocean E(B)V workflows, from data collection to data products

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Abstract—The Southern Ocean is a unique environment, and while it has been less impacted by human activities compared to other oceans, certain regions are experiencing rapid changes. These changes, driven by environmental shifts and other stressors, are putting the ecosystems of these areas at risk. While our understanding of Southern Ocean biological processes and phenomena (e.g. species distributions, feeding ecology and reproduction) has greatly improved in recent years, biological data for the region remain patchy, sparse, and unstandardized depending on taxonomic group. Due to the limited availability of standardized observations, modeling and predicting the responses of Antarctic marine ecosystems to climate change pose significant challenges. These challenges are compounded by the simultaneous rise in anthropogenic pressures such as fishing and tourism, making it even more complex to anticipate ecosystem reactions accurately. Standardized observations are required for ecosystem-based management in Antarctica and the Southern Ocean, including the establishment of protected areas (such as Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), Antarctic Specially Protected Areas (ASPAs), and Antarctic Specially Managed Areas (ASMAs)). Synergistic methods for identifying monitoring variables include Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs), Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), Essential Climate Variables (ECVs), and ecosystem Essential Ocean Variables (eEOVs). EBVs, which could be integrated into SOOS (Southern Ocean Observing System), SOOSmap, and other global information systems, bridge the gap between primary observations and biodiversity assessments by measuring the status of key indicators and describing their trends (see <https://soosymposium2023.au/essential-variables-workshop/>).

This workshop is a UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development endorsed activity.

Keywords—Southern Ocean, Essential (Biodiversity) Variables, Ocean Observations, Marine Ecosystems

1. Workshop goals

Essential Variables inventory for the Southern Ocean. Compile an inventory of Essential Variables

(EVs) relevant to the Southern Ocean, drawing on existing initiatives by the Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO-BON) and the Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON).

Data requirements and gap analysis. Assess the data requirements for calculating identified EVs. Bring to light existing data gaps that hinder the accurate determination of these variables.

Prioritization of Essential Variables. Establish a priority list for EVs based on their significance to Southern Ocean biodiversity, ecosystem function and services, as well as the urgency of their inclusion in monitoring efforts, considering factors such as ecological importance, sensitivity to climate change, and relevance to policy and management decisions.

Identification of workflows and tools. Identify and analyze existing workflows and tools for processing and analyzing biodiversity data. Determine their applicability to Southern Ocean data and identify any gaps that need to be addressed.

Framework development for data transformation. Develop a robust framework for converting publicly available Southern Ocean biodiversity data into relevant Essential Variables. This should include methodologies for data integration, standardization, and quality control, ensuring consistency and reliability.

2. Convenors background

- The SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portal (Biodiversity.aq) : This portal, funded by the Belgian Science Policy Office (BelSPO) and recognized as an official SCAR product, leads the development of an

innovative antarctic biodiversity information system. Aligned with the principles of the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), functioning as a data management tool and repository for biodiversity-related research, it facilitates access to a network of distributed databases of relevance to Antarctic and Southern Ocean biodiversity.

- Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS.aq) : This entity acts as a coordinating body to enhance Southern Ocean observations and ensure the delivery of Southern Ocean data across nations, organizations, programmes and stakeholders, and to provide the infrastructure for organization of community networks to develop sustained observing systems and syntheses of existing Southern Ocean datasets. It is a joint initiative of the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) and the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR).
- Australian Antarctic Division (AAD) : The Australian Antarctic Division leads the Australian Government's scientific program in Antarctica, with research priorities including climate change, the conservation of Antarctic and Southern Ocean wildlife, and the sustainable management of Southern Ocean fisheries.
- The Expert Group on Antarctic Biodiversity Informatics (EG-ABI) : This is a group established by the SCAR and its primary objective is to advance the application and development of biodiversity informatics within the SCAR community. EG-ABI facilitates collaboration among researchers and supports initiatives related to data access, integration, analysis and synthesis in Antarctic and Southern Ocean biodiversity science. The group also promotes the use of open software and data in computational biodiversity research by providing resources such as software tools, collaborative platforms and educational materials to assist scientists, policymakers and others in leveraging biodiversity data effectively.
- ADVANCE : The Antarctic bioDiVersity dAta iNfras-truCturE project, funded by BELSPO, is a collaborative effort involving organizations such as SOOS, the Australian Antarctic Division, EMODnet, WoRMS, GBIF and OBIS, that aims to enhance the coordination and interoperability of tools and facilities globally to transform Southern Ocean and Antarctic biodiversity data into research and policy-relevant data products. It involves creating a Virtual Research Infrastructure (VRI) for the Antarctic and Southern Ocean region, extending the SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portal and integrating with international

platforms such as SOOSmap.

3. Global context

Currently, there is a variety of Essential Variables for understanding climate, biodiversity, and other environmental changes (e.g. ecosystem Essential Ocean Variables (eEOVs), Essential Climate Variables (ECVs), Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) and Essential Ecosystem Service Variables (EESVs)). Those variables have either been previously produced or are still under development.

To advance the collection, sharing, and use of biodiversity information for monitoring purposes, the concept of Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) was introduced (Pereira et al. 2013; Navarro et al. 2017), providing a way to aggregate the many biodiversity observations collected through different methods, such as in situ monitoring or remote sensing. EBVs can be visualized as biodiversity measurements at a single place across time, or as observations from several locations aggregated in a time series of maps (see <https://geobon.org/ebvs/what-are-ebvs/>).

The Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) of the World Meteorological Organisation regularly evaluates the state of global climate observations, with expert panels precisely defining Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) as the cornerstone for systematically monitoring Earth's evolving climate. A subset of ECVs have informed the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), representing key physical, chemical, and biological observations that provide essential information about the state of the ocean and its role in the Earth system. Similarly to the observations that inform EBVs, EOVs can be derived from in-situ and satellite observations, and are designed to allow the gathering of data at a global scale for delivery into global assessments and processes (Miloslavich et al. 2018). Close collaboration between GEO-BON and GOOS ensures that both the EBVs and EOVs data schemes support interoperability between systems (Muller-Karger et al. 2018).

The creation of Essential Ecosystem Service Variables (EESVs) is underway in order to offer a complete picture of how the relationships between nature and humans are evolving over time. These EESVs are intended to improve monitoring of progress towards the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Agenda 2030. Balvanera et al. 2022 suggested an initial list of EESV classes that include ecological supply, anthropogenic contribution, demand, usage, instrumental values and relational values.

4. Structure

A brief introduction on the workshop topic was conducted, followed by a qualitative assessment of participants' expertise levels about it. A round-table session then allowed participants to introduce themselves and get acquainted. Participants were subsequently divided into five groups, according to their expertise/interests, to identify and discuss relevant Essential Variables in monitoring Antarctic and Southern Ocean ecosystems, with the goal of selecting a series of priority variables based on community interest and feasibility. The results from each group were then communicated and discussed in plenary, generating synthetic shared documents. This structure, consisting of a subject introduction, breakout group talks, a general discussion, and finally, a global report, was repeated for each stage of the workshop to achieve the defined objectives: defining priority variables, listing available and missing data required for the discussed variables, establishing workflows for variable calculations, and ultimately developing a comprehensive framework defining standards from data collection to data products for the Antarctic and Southern Ocean regions.

5. Results

5.1. Sea ice breakout group.

Participants. Andrew Meijers, Katherine Tattersall, Klaus Meiners, Sian Henley, Stuart Corney

Background summary. The sea ice breakout group suggested a pragmatic approach by using existing work from GOOS. They cataloged mature EOVs linked to sea ice properties (e.g. sea ice concentration, sea ice thickness, sea ice age, etc.). This already existing repository of information, once organized and adapted towards the specifics of the Southern Ocean, could serve as a robust foundation. It seemed that a number of these EOVs would demand steps of calculations and/or standardization, or even necessitate direct observational data as a starting point to become sufficiently insightful in the Antarctic context. The group noted that while some EVs are ice-specific, there are also many EVs from other realms (e.g. pelagic EVs) that could be measured in sea ice, such as nutrients concentration and species composition. The priority tasks identified by this group were to determine which "pelagic" EOVs would need a unique sea ice EOV (or whether the existing EOV could just be measured in sea ice), whether derived or observed variables would be most useful in providing the information required, and finally, why and how these variables would be obtained. For example, in the case of carbon export production, they expressed an interest in measuring the flux of ice-derived carbon into the ocean but asked what would be

needed to measure it properly. Those questions are important considerations in avoiding duplication of efforts on EOVs.

It's important to recognise that the EOVs represent particular phenomena (e.g. zooplankton composition) with the actual observations that contribute to that phenomena sitting underneath as sub-variables (e.g. acoustic measurements of krill swarms) and the associated environmental correlates that drive that composition - that is, provide context to the observations (e.g. proximity to sea ice), identified as supporting variables. This allows for key linkages between EOVs and associated data flows to be mapped out.

Recently developed sea ice-specific Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) (Lavergne et al. 2022) are generally cost-effective for describing the physical properties of sea ice. Existing satellite observations are indeed well suited to measure properties of the upper layer of ice, however, it remains difficult to determine the processes and properties occurring at the bottom of the sea ice or underneath it.

Finally, specific components, or realms/habitats, can be recognized for the sea ice ecosystem: sea ice itself, snow covering sea ice, platelet layer occurring beneath sea ice as well as leads in sea ice. Variables might be adapted to each of these components but not all of the variables will be relevant to all four realms.

Data gaps. Harsh conditions and restricted access inherent to the Southern Ocean and Antarctica contribute to a notable lack of winter under-ice measurements, particularly regarding the biological realm. The existing data is predominantly related to the summer season, creating a spatial and temporal bias that hampers a comprehensive assessment of the state of the ecosystem.

Moreover, there is a tendency to exclude in-ice parameters : when an ice core is sampled, only measurements which are relevant to the project collecting the core are taken, even if other potentially informative measurements could easily be obtained with little to no extra cost. This is mainly because data collection is tailored to the specific objectives of the research group involved. In certain cases, this could nevertheless arise from logistical challenges and/or added costs of routine measurement. This exclusion could contribute to a potential oversight in understanding critical facets of the environment. Certain plankton and sea-ice algae groups are not routinely measured, primarily due to the fact that their association with ice represents genuine logistical challenges in terms of access and operations. Addressing these challenges and closing the existing gaps is imperative for a more holistic understanding of the Southern Ocean's sea ice-related ecosystems and their intricate dynamics. Exploring innovative techniques could help in advancing

Figure 1. Photo by Henrique Setim on Unsplash

Southern Ocean biodiversity monitoring. For example, incorporating under-ice remote sensing through transmitted radiance spectra, facilitated by remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) and potentially Argo-Floats (with under-ice avoidance), could introduce a new dimension to data acquisition. Additionally, leveraging hydroacoustic methods, like using backscatter as a phytoplankton biomass/concentration proxy, and employing camera work with advanced image analysis could also expedite and standardize traditional methods, such as microscopy, for the identification of ice algae species composition.

A major consideration that remains is the definition of the appropriate spatial resolution to measure these sea ice variables. The vertical resolution, it is suggested, should align with prevalent ice core sampling and analysis practices, often conducted in approximately ten-centimeter increments. This should ensure compatibility and coherence with already established methodologies. The horizontal resolution would benefit from being higher than that employed for in-water measurements, due to the strong spatial heterogeneity within the complex sea-ice matrix. This more nuanced approach should have the potential to enhance the accuracy and granularity of collected data.

A table 1 summarizing all the Sea Ice Variables identified during the workshop is provided in Section 9 of

this document, as well as a series of linked workflows, with varying degrees of detail, proposed by this group. While most of the Sea Ice Variables consist of already mature Climate and Ocean Variables, some might need additional development to be really useful in a Southern Ocean context (e.g. calculation, standardization).

5.2. Plankton breakout group.

Participants. Irene Schloss, Kerrie Swadling, Luke Brokensha, Ruth Eriksen, Svenja Halfter

Background summary and data gaps. The plankton breakout group chose to reuse the concept of Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs), which was introduced by GEO BON to advance the collection, sharing and use of biodiversity information (Pereira et al. 2013; Navarro et al. 2017). Thus, the information gathered was sorted in accordance with the 6 already defined EBVs classes, which are :

- Genetic composition : internal genetic diversity, genetic differentiation, effective population size, inbreeding
- Species populations : distribution and abundance
- Species traits : phenology, morphology, physiology, movement, reproduction

- Community composition : community abundance, taxonomic diversity, trait diversity, interaction diversity
- Ecosystem structure : life cover fraction, ecosystem distribution, ecosystem vertical profile
- Ecosystem functioning : marine primary productivity, ecosystem phenology (e.g. spring bloom), ecosystem disturbances

The breakout group highlighted the existence of several databases housing valuable plankton biodiversity data, such as AODN/NZODN, SO-CPR, KRILLBASE, COPEPOD and PANGAEA. However, it's noteworthy that these databases predominantly focus on phytoplankton.

Regarding the *Genetic Composition EBV class*, collecting genetic data related to harmful algal bloom (HAB) toxins and lesser-known small-sized plankton as well as developing sampling methods applicable across all plankton size classes was suggested. The group also advised the implementation of a taxon criteria. HABs and calcifiers emerged as candidates, given their ecological significance, potential impact on the broader marine ecosystem and vulnerability to ocean-scale changes like acidification, respectively.

In the context of the *Species Populations class*, the breakout group emphasized the limited availability of information on the distribution and abundance of particular groups of plankton, and this for all the broader categories such as zooplankton, phytoplankton, ichthyoplankton, etc. Even if data encompassing all size classes within these diverse plankton groups is needed, the breakout group prioritized the study of calcifiers, diatoms, and dinoflagellates because of their susceptibility to the effects of ocean acidification. Environmental DNA (eDNA) could be a powerful tool for monitoring species distributions and community composition. While Southern Ocean continuous plankton recorder (CPR) surveys are coordinated under the auspices of the Global Alliance of CPR Surveys (GACS), there is not yet a publicly-accessible and unified data set of all Southern Ocean surveys.

The *Community Composition class* was considered generally well covered except for the smaller plankton classes. When examining the *Species Traits EBV class*, the breakout group identified species phenology as the highest priority for data collection, the timing of life cycle events, such as reproduction, migration, and seasonal occurrences, being crucial for understanding the dynamics of Southern Ocean ecosystems. Databases highlighting trophic traits and distinguishing between autotrophs, heterotrophs, and mixotrophs, were deemed valuable because. While some species traits are addressed, big gaps

regarding plankton remain. Indeed, traits for specific plankton species are often extrapolated from broader taxonomic groups, leading to potential inaccuracies in our understanding.

The exploration of the *Ecosystem Structure class* led the plankton breakout group to advise the delineation of oceanographic zones (epipelagic, mesopelagic, etc.) to more accurately encapsulate the diverse components and properties of Southern Ocean ecosystems. A proposed observation for capturing information on these ecosystems is the size spectrum of plankton, as body size determines basic processes of organisms, such as metabolic rate, generation time and speed of locomotion. In ecosystems, size structures can define species interactions including trophic positions, pathways and magnitude of carbon flow through the system components (Inessa Corney 2024, personal communication). The group then suggested a more frequent use of stable isotopes, which can offer valuable insights into trophic interactions and energy transfer within the ecosystem. Mobilizing and contributing data to databases such as SO-Diet, a resource developed by the SCAR, seemed to also hold potential in consolidating information on Southern Ocean trophic dynamics. Given the plankton assemblages complexity, the breakout group acknowledged that simply adapting existing Essential Climate Variable (ECV)/Essential Ocean Variable (EOV) workflows may not yield sufficiently relevant information. Identifying what modifications/updates to current EOVs (as articulated in their specification sheets) is probably needed to avoid this limitation.

Capturing the full suite of plankton in an ecosystem poses significant challenges but potential new variables or innovative measurement approaches, such as eDNA, could be key in this regard. Identifying what those new variables would look like, if those variables are already captured by EOVs and if not, whether they are truly "new variables" or sub-variables that can be incorporated into the current EOVs would be of great interest.

In addressing the *Ecosystem Functioning EBV class*, the breakout group highlighted that surface chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) measurements from satellites, while valuable, are still strongly influenced and limited by factors such as cloud cover, the polar night, and sea ice. Algorithms used to derive them are also not yet well calibrated for the Southern Ocean (Zeng, Xu, and Fischer 2016). Additionally, these measurements often lack information on secondary and bacterial productions, offering an incomplete representation of this ecosystem's biogeochemical dynamics.

One other major challenge identified is the localized nature of current observations of ocean biogeochemistry, ship-based observations being seasonally limited. More generally, there is a pressing need to improve the visibil-

ity, access, and extraction of plankton data from existing repositories. The ability to access information in near-real-time could significantly enhance our knowledge, at a pace more aligned with the dynamic changes occurring in the Southern Ocean.

5.3. Benthic breakout group.

Participants. Heike Link, Jan Jansen, Nicole Hill, Petra ten Hoopen

Background summary and data gaps. The benthic breakout also aligned with the GEO BON EBV framework, working with the six EBV classes in mind. They are listed under Section 5.2.

In terms of *Genetic Composition*, the group emphasized the importance of embracing metagenomics as an analytical tool. Metagenomics provides a means for studying community composition and ecological interactions. This kind of analytical approach is deemed feasible for studying the very small, like meiofauna. The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) databases was pointed as the relevant resource for genomic data access.

Within the *Species Populations class*, the distribution patterns of commercial fish and invertebrates have been highlighted as particularly relevant. For marine invertebrates, an initial prioritization of certain taxonomic groups and areas is needed. Defining indicator taxa, potentially complemented with genetic information, is suggested as a strategic approach. Then, the group acknowledged that existing data, even for non-commercially exploited species, might be available and mobilizable, but raising the question of where to locate and access this information. Most taxonomic subsets from scientific trawls are restricted to selected areas but some are available at a circumpolar level. These subsets are hosted on platforms such as the Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS), the biodiversity.aq portal or described in the Biodiversity Atlas. Some Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME) taxa are recorded in fishery data at depths of 550 meters and beyond for specific areas. However, caution is advised in interpreting these records due to potential biases and gear selectivity issues inherent in fishery data (e.g. by-catch). The breakout group also mentioned the possibility of observing fish nests with underwater imagery. Regarding species abundance data, imagery for the entire continental shelf (from 200 meters and below) should be released soon (see preprint of “The Antarctic Seafloor Annotated Imagery Database” at <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2023.02.16.528770v1>). This kind of information is currently mostly available for shallow waters near research stations, such as Casey/Davis, Ross Sea and Rothera.

While the spatial coverage remains limited, there is recognition that at least some temporal data is already accessible for analysis. Furthermore, some abundance data for infauna, meiofauna, and polychaetes is accessible in PANGAEA, predominantly for the Weddell Sea. There is also a notable lack of repeated surveys when considering broader areas, strongly hampering the temporal coverage. The group recommended the standardization of methods throughout various aspects of data collection and analysis, or at least the mapping of the data to a common framework. This emphasis was particularly directed towards imagery data collection and its subsequent scoring process. The call for standardization extended to the collection and quantification of trawl and infaunal data. The breakout group further proposed to consider nursery areas, especially for fish, as an aspect meriting inclusion in the biodiversity.aq wiki. For example, nests of ice fish discovered in Weddell Sea could be routinely monitored via camera for size and number. There might be possibilities for discovering similar nests in other shallow water areas around the coast (e.g. *Pleuragramma* sp. eggs and larvae in platelet ice). The abundance of non-commercial benthic/demersal fish and invertebrate species was recognized as a valuable indicator. Additionally, the group proposed the monitoring of alien marine taxa introduced through hull fouling and ballast water. They also recommended prioritizing vulnerable taxa susceptible to ocean acidification, including calcifiers, species sensitive to thermal tolerances, and those affected by changes in sea ice.

In the *Species Traits EBV class*, the benthic group considered phenology-related questions but acknowledged that their relevance to benthic systems may be limited or just unknown by the group (e.g. the duration of blooms could potentially be more crucial than the timing).

For the *Ecosystem Structure class*, the proposal of live cover fraction, particularly for suspension feeders, is identified as an intriguing avenue. Ecosystem distribution variables are suggested to be splitted into two separate categories: shallow/nearshore and offshore environments. Each category may indeed be more influenced by certain characteristics, such as macroalgal dominance for the nearshore environments and epibenthic or suspension/detritus-dominated conditions for offshore areas. These characteristics are recommended to be evaluated in relation to a sea ice component.

In terms of the *Ecosystem Functioning class*, the group advised measuring, particularly in shallow waters (including shelves), ecosystem disturbances such as iceberg scour, bottom fishing, scientific bottom trawling, sedimentation (especially in areas of increased glacial melt) and monitoring for CCAMLR Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VME).

The benthic group also explored the identification of ecosystem Essential Ocean Variables (eEOVs), which are based on the Framework on Ocean Observing (FOO) and were developed for the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) in 2016. Initially identifying appropriate taxonomic groups might be useful to define these variables properly. They could be defined based on taxonomy, functionality (e.g. depositional filter feeder, suspension feeder) or abundance. The group leaned towards abundance as perhaps the more manageable and practical basis to work with.

The participants of this group acknowledged the inherent difficulties associated with broad-scale, direct observations of benthic systems in the Southern Ocean. Current efforts are often conducted at a smaller, primarily regional scale, which poses challenges in detecting and understanding larger-scale patterns and changes. Genomic methods have been proposed as a promising tool to overcome some of these challenges, although the standardization of these methods is a necessary step for their effective implementation. The utility of historical trawl/core data has been discussed: while core sampling time and location may be known in some cases, data is not always readily available. The limited spatial coverage of currently tractable methods poses constraints on the ability to detect changes. The current focus may be more conducive to establishing baselines rather than enabling the detection of dynamic changes in benthic ecosystems. Furthermore, the group raised questions about the utility of relatively easy-to-report measures of benthic cover, drawing an analogy to measures such as coral cover in other ecosystems. Parameters such as suspension feeder cover, deposit feeder cover, sessile/mobile organisms cover and total cover hold potential value in offering a more accessible depiction of benthic community composition. It's important to note that the utility of cover measures might vary across different habitats. While they may be suitable for hard substrate environments, their relevance for soft substrates could be considerably lower. As a result, these metrics may not be universally applicable to all benthic areas.

Finally, the breakout group put forward major gaps, recommendations and tools deemed crucial for advancing research in benthic ecosystems in the Southern Ocean. Concerning species abundance, while there is some availability on OBIS, data remains limited. There is a need for easier access to additional information, beyond mere presence records, as it would enable the reconstruction of abundance datasets. For *Species Traits* and *Ecosystem Structure*, there is a significant gap in data availability, or the group participants were not aware of existing datasets. In addressing the *Ecosystem Functioning class*, linking primary productivity duration to seafloor communities

could be a potential avenue to fill existing gaps, utilizing the fact that primary productivity regime is a predictor of benthic community type (Jansen et al. 2018). A functional aspect that lacks data is the contribution from the benthos in terms of carbon assimilation and remineralization. The absence of data on ecosystem disturbance is noted as a notable gap.

Among the recommendations made, the breakout group proposed the establishment of a live database or map. This dynamic platform would facilitate the collection of imagery, trawl and sediment core data, with a focus on including relevant metadata, such as the system used and its orientation. They also highlighted the need for a common infrastructure dedicated to benthic imagery, serving as a centralized repository for storing, exploring, and visualizing benthic imagery data. Such a repository could be part of a more generic infrastructure that is able to support image data life cycle. Essential questions regarding benthic variables were raised, such as which part of the benthos and what depths are most important to quantify but also whether to prioritize functional groups, sessile organisms, total cover, calcifiers, structural taxa or factors like the weight/abundance of infauna. In short, these inquiries underscored the need for clarity in defining research priorities to guide future investigations.

5.4. Mesopelagic breakout group.

Background summary and data gaps. During the workshop, the absence of a dedicated breakout group for the mesopelagic theme was noted, primarily due to the lack of expertise present in the room, coupled with the limited time available and the number of participants. Consequently, addressing the mesopelagic thematic in depth was challenging. Nonetheless, participants expressed a keen interest in prioritizing this aspect in future activities. The workshop underscored the significance of the mesopelagic zone within the Southern Ocean ecosystem. Organisms inhabiting this zone serve as key linkages, not only facilitating the flow of energy from lower to higher trophic levels but also bridging the gap between the pelagic and benthic zones. In contrast to the relatively well-sampled upper pelagic zone (within the upper 200m), the mesopelagic area remains under-sampled, largely due to the requirement for larger gear and longer deployment times associated with traditional net trawls. However, ongoing technological advancements, such as camera-based systems and acoustic methods, hold promise for more frequent and comprehensive observations in the future. The discussion also touched upon the potential of acoustic technologies, with mention of initiatives like the Southern Ocean Network of Acoustics (SONA). SONA aims to elucidate the broad-scale distribution of mid-trophic level secondary producers by

Figure 2. Photo by Bob Brewer on Unsplash

implementing a self-sustaining, long-term acoustic observation strategy within the international observing and modelling communities.

5.5. Top-predators breakout group.

Participants. Andrea Walters, Anna MacDonald, Angus Henderson, Noémie Friscourt, Sophia Volzke

Background summary and data gaps. This breakout group initiated their discussions by posing several fundamental questions, including the relevance of creating top-predators variables, the need for additional work in this area, and the existence of data that supports such endeavors. The group focused on identifying existing Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) that could be adapted to the specific conditions of the Southern Ocean, with varying degrees of required work.

Within the *Biology and Ecosystems EOV class*, data on abundance as well as on distribution of sea birds and mammals was considered as key. The need for this kind of data could be addressed with the establishment of a Southern Ocean Population Trends Database/Repository, drawing inspiration from the Retrospective Analysis of Antarctic Tracking Data (RAATD) project. This database could eventually be included in the Antarctic OBIS node. Furthermore, the breakout group recognized the relevance of fish abundance and predator/prey linkages. There is value in leveraging existing databases such

as the Myctobase and Southern Ocean Diet (SO-Diet) SCAR initiatives.

In the *Biochemistry EOV class*, the breakout group emphasized the importance of key parameters such as oxygen, nutrients and stable carbon isotopes (N, S, O, and Hg).

In the *Physics EOV class*, a range of physical parameters was considered essential for studying the Southern Ocean. These include sea ice, sea surface height, sea surface temperature, surface currents, subsurface currents and salinity of the water column.

For cross-disciplinary considerations, attention was drawn towards human impacts (e.g. marine debris), stressing the need for thorough monitoring and understanding of presence and impact in the Southern Ocean. Additionally, it was suggested to incorporate data on contaminants to study the prevalence/effects of pollutants in the region and to include information related to various other human disturbances such as marine traffic, noise pollution and fisheries activities (including the critical issue of by-catch).

The breakout group then evaluated the situation within the Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBV) framework. In the course of their discussions, they recognized that not all aspects within the *Genetic Composition class* (e.g. the spatial and temporal variability in the intraspecific genetic composition) necessarily require DNA data. There is already some genetic diversity data available but the exact species to which this data applies remains to be

clearly determined. Genetic studies for individual species do exist but not yet a central database that collates key summary statistics, sustaining EBVs. With OBIS supporting publication of genetic data, it was suggested to bring together these studies onto the portal, thus centralizing data on a single point of access. Concerning genetic differentiation, the breakout group assumed that the number of genetic units could be estimated based on current expert knowledge of population structure. However, they noted that the genetic distance variable would require more data, which is currently unavailable. The effective population size variable needs substantial work. As a potential answer, transformed census population size could be used as a proxy. For the inbreeding variable, the community needs detailed knowledge of species before meaningful assessments can be made.

Discussions within the *Species Population EBV class* revealed that considerable data should already exist for certain taxa such as mammals, fish and birds (e.g. emperor penguins), although this statement is mostly true for birds and pinnipeds. We have well sampled areas close to stations because they can be easily reached, hence collection tends to be biased across space and time. This often means that winter data is very rarely collected, and so we have incomplete understanding of life cycles throughout the year. In recent years, tracking data significantly helped in reducing this spatial-temporal gap, especially for mammals and seabirds; stock assessment conducted under CCAMLR for commercial fish species also provided information on population abundance. The available data quality varies considerably, highlighting the need for significant effort in standardization and data sharing (Lapatas et al. 2015). Additionally, there is a recognized necessity to broaden the focus beyond currently sampled species. Indeed, while data on species distributions is abundant for some, there is a notable lack of information for others. Regarding existing data, the group mentioned RAATD and MOVEBANK for seals, MAPPPD for penguins, IWC and HappyWhale for whales, Myctobase for fish and it noted the absence, or ignorance, of a reference database for squids. Genetic studies can be a relevant source of information with lots of eDNA datasets including species detection but they still need standardized methods and collated data to really inform EBVs. In terms of species abundances, there is a wealth of data available but primarily for a limited number of commercial fish species. The breakout group advised the creation of a metadatabase, potentially managed by the EG-BAMM SCAR expert group, focused on demographic information. This would include details such as species, year and region, without necessarily containing raw data. They also advised the extension of the CCAMLR Ecosystem Monitoring Program (CEMP). This

initiative extension would cover key ecological aspects including abundance, distribution (both breeding and foraging), diet and tracking information. The CEMP already gathers information about seals and seabirds population trends. In general, distribution and abundance data could be complemented with additional tracking campaigns and sighting surveys. The Australian East Antarctic Monitoring Program (EAMP) could also be of interest regarding a potential extension.

In the discussions surrounding the *Species Traits class*, the breakout group noted the existence of substantial data in terms of phenology, for mammals and birds. However, it did not provide any specific mention regarding the status of the variables related to morphology, physiology, movement and reproduction for these organisms groups. Concerning *Community Composition*, the breakout group did not elaborate on the status or relevance of variables such as community abundance, taxonomic/phylogenetic diversity and trait diversity. However, the group placed significant emphasis on variables related to diet and predator/prey interactions, for which some data is already easily accessible from the SO-Diet SCAR database. The breakout group found the *Ecosystem Structure* and *Ecosystem Functioning* as relevant aspects, not only for top predators but also for preyfields (e.g. plankton, fish).

6. Environmental variable to workflow

Before describing new variables, it is important to conduct an evaluation to determine the extent to which the measurements associated with the variable are already captured by existing variables. Additionally, assessing if existing variables could be modified to accommodate Southern Ocean-specific observations would ensure that duplication is avoided and that the variables align with what already exists. Given the limited duration of the workshop, this could not be done in detail by participants. A point was also made regarding language used when describing variables. It should always be unambiguous and allow to know if the concerned EV is a direct observation, which is not so common for actual EVs, or if it refers to a collection of observations that contribute to a variable. Here are suggested requirements and steps to go from a candidate Essential Variable to a mature Workflow.

Scientific description and justification.

- Provide a comprehensive scientific description and justification for the proposed EV, outlining its relevance, including policy implications, and, if applicable, cost justifications
- Include guidance on potential decisions in subsequent steps, derived from the scientific justification

Plain-language description and calculation.

- Incorporate information on data collection and archival methods :
 - Provide insight into how the initial data used for the EV was collected and stored (e.g. field methods, sampling procedures, data acquisition from existing repositories, etc.), including limitations and comments on data source usage
 - Explain any standard or protocol followed in the collection and archival of the data, ensuring data quality and reproducibility

Reference implementation in code.

- Present a reference implementation to provide a clear and reliable example that demonstrates how the concept or algorithm should be implemented
- Subject the implementation to peer review to validate its accurate representation and to identify and rectify any error
- Enhance transparency by allowing others to scrutinize the code, promoting confidence in the accuracy of the EV calculation
- Establish a basis for comparison, enabling the assessment of proposed EVs against already existing ones
- If an R package is developed, allow peer review and improvements via issue opening using rOpenSci

Calculation of EV data using reference implementation.

- Generate EV data using the reference implementation
- Designate the produced dataset as the "endorsed"/"official" data for the EV, complete with a DOI and link to content of previous steps
- Provide the community with a reliable data product and a comparison dataset for implementation testing or other purposes
- Provide guidelines and training on how and where to submit datasets allowing the calculation of the "official" EV

Additional considerations for incorporation at a later stage. Incorporate data upload as part of the workflow, with varying levels of validation. Address questions about workflow granularity, considering whether an overarching workflow or multiple individual workflows are more efficient. Developed workflows could also be modular (see <https://books.ropensci.org/targets/>). Discuss the chain of custody of samples through data processing and data publication. Outline steps for standardization, including raw data aggregation, intermediate product creation through a standardized pipeline and any subsequent process.

7. Where to focus next?

Indicating who the potential users and stakeholders of the Southern Ocean-specific variables are (e.g. scientists, policymakers, conservation organizations, etc.) and how this audience will use the variables in their work and decision-making processes (e.g. research, policy decision, etc.) seems like one of the top priority to address. By considering the real audience, while keeping the outcomes of the workshop in mind, we can more effectively frame the discussion on Southern Ocean-specific variables and provide valuable insights for future research and development efforts in the region.

Questions arise from this point of view : How appropriate are the EBVs to capture Southern Ocean observations ? What in association might be needed in developing a set of Southern Ocean specific variables ?

Priorities

Sea ice breakout group.

1. Enhance understanding and monitoring of sea ice-related ecosystems in the Southern Ocean
2. Define specific pelagic Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) for sea ice and determine which require adaptations
3. Address the lack of winter under-ice measurements
4. Incorporate innovative techniques like under-ice remote sensing, ice-tethered observatories and robotic floats equipped with ice-specific sensors to overcome logistical challenges and biases
5. Define appropriate resolutions for optimal data accuracy and granularity

Plankton breakout group.

1. Address data gaps for smaller plankton classes

Figure 3. Photo by Paul Carroll on Unsplash

2. Collect genetic data on harmful algal blooms, small-sized plankton and species distribution/abundance data on calcifiers, diatoms, and dinoflagellates
 3. Unify CPR surveys data
 4. Collect phenology data at species level for plankton (currently, mainly krill and *Rhincalanus gigas* have life stage counts)
 5. Delineate oceanographic zones
 6. Explore a potential criteria: size spectrum of plankton
 7. Improve visibility, access, extraction (aim at near real-time) of plankton data from existing repositories (feasible now for Chl-a but not for CPR data since there is a lag between the collection, analysis and data publication steps)
2. Standardize data collection and analysis methods, especially for imagery techniques and the subsequent scoring
 3. Explore the relevance of nursery areas, alien marine taxa and vulnerable taxa monitoring
 4. Measure ecosystem disturbances, particularly in shallow waters
 5. Establish a dynamic database/map for imagery, trawl and sediment core data

Top-predators group.

1. Create a population trends repository, for abundance and distribution of birds and mammals
2. Focus on predator/prey linkages
3. Reuse EOVs, for biochemistry and physical parameters
4. Monitor human impacts (e.g. contaminants, marine traffic, noise pollution and fisheries activities)
5. Create a centralized genetic diversity database, focusing on summary statistics

Benthic breakout group.

1. Use metagenomics to analyze small-sized organisms (e.g. meiofauna)

6. Shift the focus to other species than birds and mammals (e.g. fish and squids)
7. Create a metadatabase for demographic information, extending the CCAMLR Ecosystem Monitoring Program
8. Identify key species to collect data on morphology, physiology, movement and reproduction

Workplan

Goals.

1. Identify candidate Essential Variables (EVs) that are feasible/tractable in current circumstances and implement them on biodiversity.aq and/or SOOSmap. This integration will allow the centralizing of information and prevent duplication of effort. More importantly, selected variables will serve as a demonstration and a testing ground, laying the foundation for a systematic framework. The success of this initial phase will pave the way for the addition of new EVs over time.
2. Publish a review paper that documents the outcomes of this workshop, the process of identifying and implementing EVs and, finally, the establishment of a systematic framework. This paper should provide a structured blueprint for integrating Southern Ocean focused EVs.

Proposed Titles.

- To be determined

Proposed Journals.

- Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene (IF 3.9)
 - SOOS Symposium Special Issue : Understanding the trajectory and implication of a changing Southern Ocean: the need for an integrated observing system
- Frontiers in Marine Science (IF 3.7)
 - Research Topic: Best Practices in Ocean Observing
 - Deadline for submission : 31 december 2024
- Biodiversity Data Journal (IF 1.3)
- Data Science Journal (IF 0.428)

8. EBV workflows

8.1. Sea ice variables. The sea ice breakout group focused on chlorophyll-a variables because they can be derived into proxies for ice algal biomass, which is considered a key early season food source for pelagic herbivores (e.g. krill (commercially harvested)). For a measure of biological productivity in marine systems, see Henley et al. 2019. Before developing any new EV, looking at plankton ECV and EOVS specification sheets would ensure that observations and data flows will be compatible with those, supporting interoperability.

8.1.1. Chlorophyll-a concentration.

Sub-habitats. Sea ice (cores), snow, platelet ice, leads in sea ice (water sample).

Data gap. Spatial coverage between the 0.01 to 100 m² scales.

Methods. Melt ice sample in hypersaline or filtered sea water, filter, fluorometry (described in Miller et al. 2015). There is a variety of methods to extract chlorophyll-a from filters, followed by Chl-a determination by fluorometry or HPLC. The output is a field observed value in µg/L. It may be interesting to measure particulate organic carbon (POC) concentration simultaneously to quantify the carbon biomass in sea ice. POC measurements are more expensive but can be informative for understanding the carbon-to-Chl-a ratio, which is a biogeochemically relevant parameter. There is very limited capability to determine the extent of carbon contributed to the Biological Carbon Pump (BCP) through sea ice primary production and even less is known about contributions from secondary production in the ice.

Essential field sheet metadata. Date, Time, Lat, Lon, Station No., Water depth, Ice thickness, Snow thickness, Freeboard, Core ID, Depth from top to bottom of ice core section (depth from top of sea ice surface, e.g. 30-40 cm).

Essential laboratory metadata/methods. Filter size (GF/F nominal pore size 0.7 µm), Gentle vacuum filtration at 0.1 bar, Preservation method: in liquid nitrogen or below -80°C, Calculation of µg/L, Standard calculation method/algorithm, Standard CSV data format (SCAR ASPeCt-Bio), Metadata header and CSV parameters (template sheet).

Pipeline for publishing. Chl-a data is not appropriate to the Darwin Core format (DwC, used by GBIF and OBIS for taxonomic data). Best integrated sea ice data publishing platform : SOOSmap. Researchers to supply standardized csv format. Upload to a virtual laboratory hosting (e.g. jupyter notebooks) which will transform

data to agreed transfer format : DwC. DwC files can easily be loaded to IPT and delivered to GBIF, OBIS, SOOS and others as appropriate.

8.1.2. Transmitted radiance spectra. It constitutes an emerging technology to measure chlorophyll-a in sea ice, this is not yet a variable in its own right but rather a method to measure a sub-variable. It should help derive ice-algal Chl-a estimates from under-ice spectral radiation.

Sub-habitats. Sea ice (cores), snow, platelet ice, leads in sea ice.

Methods. Under-ice remote sensing (ROVs, bioArgo) (described in Mundy et al. 2007).

8.1.3. Emitted radiance from overturned ice floes. It constitutes an emerging technology to measure chlorophyll-a in sea ice, this is not yet a variable in its own right but rather a method to measure a sub-variable. It should help derive ice-algal Chl-a estimates from under-ice spectral radiation.

Sub-habitats. Overturned sea ice floes.

Methods. Ship (icebreaker platforms) mounted multi-spectral camera systems (SOOS - ASPeCt).

8.2. Benthic variables. See Ruhl et al. 2023 for useful insights on integrating marine observations to deliver benthic invertebrate abundance and distribution information. The benthic breakout group proposed a series of variables, deemed easiest to measure, standardize and establish as a workflow :

8.2.1. Total infaunal abundance. *Total community living in the sediment.* Typically, this kind of measurement is conducted per surface area, as infauna tends to be more abundant in the upper layers of the sediment (0-5 cm). Although some species may dig deeper, samples are usually collected down to 15-20 cm. There has been a discussion about measuring total wet weight per liter. However, standardizing samples taken at different depths per liter could introduce bias, particularly due to lower density when sampling goes to greater sediment depth. Therefore, the breakout group suggested relying on surface area with a standard protocol of 0-5 or 0-3 cm for meiofauna and 0-15 or 0-20 cm for macrofauna. It's important to note that cores are often collected in soft sediment, minimizing bias between substrates. Finally, it was suggested to split this variable by depth ranges and broad regions.

8.2.2. Total living cover. *Measured from benthic imagery.* The breakout group raised important questions regarding the definition of cover, whether it should be considered as everything that is not dead or if it should encompass different types of substrate. There are also potential challenges in implementing this variable in a more general manner. Benthic imagery can come from a wide range of habitats, unlike more specific metrics (e.g. coral cover/reef fish abundance for reef-specific evaluations), unless the variable is specifically targeted for surveys on shallow reefs (e.g. 0-50m) or along the shelf break (e.g. 500-700m, combined with a specific slope gradient), where reef habitats are common. Moreover, this variable may require longer timescales to allow sufficient data to be collected. As alternative variables that can be observed in benthic images, the breakout group proposed “community abundance of sessile species” (animals permanently attached to substrate) and/or “community abundance of suspension feeders” (animals feeding on suspended particles). These variables could equally be measured in percentage cover. Considering these variables as separate EBVs and alternatives to the “total living cover” variable could provide more flexibility in adapting to diverse benthic habitats in the Southern Ocean.

8.2.3. Genomic composition. *Taxonomic description of species present in a sample, using nucleotide sequencing of environmental DNA.* A workflow exists as a metabarcoding analysis type with results available from the MGnify database (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics>). However, further standardisation may be required.

8.2.4. Community function. *Functional profile of the community present in a sample, using sequencing of environmental RNA.* A workflow exists as a metatranscriptomics analysis type with results available from the MGnify database (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics>). However, further standardisation may be required.

8.3. Top-predators variables. It was mentioned to look closely at the specification sheet for the marine mammals EOV, which is currently being updated to incorporate new technology (e.g. census from satellites). It could provide an idea of the observations needed to deliver on distributional information. The top-predators breakout group went into the details of a particular variable and started the establishment of a workflow for it.

8.3.1. Species distributions of marine top predators. The determination of a species distribution relies on observations which are gathered through various methods such as tracking, sightings, eDNA data or a combination of those. One possible approach for this variable is to generate outputs depicting species distribution across discrete “cubes” of space and time, as highlighted in Jetz

et al. 2019).

Metadata for these observations, including "Basis of Record", should always be associated. This entails specifying the method used for each observation, with the suggestion to create Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for each method variant and reference them in the metadata. Spatial information (including height and depth) and temporal associated errors should also always be linked. Method-specific metadata, such as qPCR or metabarcoding for eDNA, the type of tag used for tracking, is also crucial. This comprehensive approach enables the future capability to filter and compare distributions obtained from different data types (e.g. tracking versus eDNA data).

Finally, the breakout group raised a specific question regarding the way to incorporate depth and height informations for species, especially considering marine species with distribution limited to specific depth ranges or those exhibiting temporal changes in depth range. For seabirds, information on height above sea level, if accurately obtainable, can become valuable for assessing risks from factors like offshore wind installations. The potential use of this variable for monitoring invasive species was also suggested.

Author contributions

AVdP, AH and BR were responsible for the workshop organization. CP wrote the manuscript. DFA, KE, BR, KS, SH, AH, SH, LB, KM, JJ, PtH, JW, RE, IC all contributed to the writing and editing of the manuscript. All authors participated in the workshop, except CP, YMG and IC.

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9. Appendix

Variable	Description
Sea ice concentration	Fraction of known ocean area covered by sea ice
Sea ice thickness	Vertical extent of the sea ice
Sea ice drift (direction, velocity)	Lateral movement of the sea ice (transport and deformation)
Sea ice age	Lifetime of the sea ice since its formation
Sea ice surface temperature	Ice or snow surface temperature
Sea ice surface albedo	Sea ice and snow surfaces’ ability to reflect solar short-wave radiation
Snow depth on sea ice	Vertical extent of the snow on top of the sea ice
Ridging rate/Structural complexity	Ice ridges forming rate
Freshwater flux at receding ice edge	Can be derived from physical parameters e.g. heat fluxes (would be individual researcher output)
Brine volume and salinity	Done but not routinely
Genetic diversity of selected sea-ice taxa	Done but not routinely
Species composition of microalgae in sea ice	Done but not routinely
Particulate organic carbon	Done but not routinely
Dissolved oxygen in frozen sea ice (oxygen content)	Done but not routinely
Oxygen production (net primary production)	Done but not routinely
Chlorophyll concentration	Done but not routinely
Nutrient concentrations	Done but not routinely
Transmitted radiance spectra	Under-ice remote sensing with ROVs and possibly Argo-Floats (under-ice avoidance)
Emitted radiance from overturned ice flows	Emerging
Backscatter as phytoplankton proxy	Measured in leads
Sympagic fauna size in platelet layer	Possible but no routine observations
Sea ice salinity	Done often but not routinely

Table 1. *Suggested Sea Ice Essential Variables*

10. External resources

- Species Traits : http://www.marinespecies.org/documents/LifeWatch%20reports/editor%20workshop%20reports/20191125_WoRMS_RAS_Trails_workshop_Report.pdf
- Biodiversity.aq wiki: https://github.com/biodiversity-aq/SO-essential_variables/wiki.
- GCOS ECVs : <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/essential-climate-variables>